

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

A REVIEW ARTICLE ON CRINUM ASIATICUM***M. Harshitha sai , M.B.L Susmitha , N. Tanmayi , R. Praveen kumar, T. Nani
K. Prathyusha and V. Sai Kishore**

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Bapatla college of Pharmacy -522101, India.

Abstract:

The Perennial bulbous herb Crinum asiaticum L. (Amaryllidaceae) is used locally for its many pharmacological qualities, which include anticancer, immune-stimulating, analgesic, antiviral, antimalarial, antibacterial, and antifungal, in addition to its widespread use as an aesthetic plant. The Amaryllidaceae family of plants has a long history of usage in traditional medicine to treat a variety of illnesses. There are fifteen distinct species of Crinum in India, and each one has a variety of biologically significant alkaloids. Nonetheless, pharmacological investigation is still necessary for some of the medicinal applications of Indian Crinum species. The research on the phytochemistry, pharmacology, and in vitro investigations of the Indian Crinum is compiled in this review.. Chemical study of the essential oils extracted from C. asiaticum showed the existence of several components such as alcohols, phenolics, fatty acids, esters, aldehydes, terpenoids, and terpenes, despite the fact that the extracts of the plant were discovered to be especially rich in alkaloids. The antioxidant, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-plas-modial, cytotoxic, anti-cancer, and antibacterial qualities of pounds from C. asiaticum have all been assessed. In summary, this plant has intriguing pharmacological qualities that merit further study, particularly in light of its potential toxicity, which could be important for the creation of phytopharmaceuticals .

Corresponding author:**M. Harshitha sai,**Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
Bapatla college of Pharmacy -522101, India.

QR code

Please cite this article in press M. Harshitha sai et al., A Review Article On Crinum Asiaticum., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (12).

INTRODUCTION:

Tropical and subtropical climates are home to *Crinum asiaticum* Linn. [*C. asiaticum*] [Amaryllidaceae family] throughout the world. There are an estimated 130 distinct flowering plant species in the genus *Crinum* L. Because *Crinum* species thrive in tropical and subtropical temperatures, they are found around the world on several continents,

including Africa, America, Asia, and Australia. They are especially abundant in alkaloids, as evidenced by a study that found 118 different alkaloids among these 130 species¹. It has been shown that the alkaloids offer a variety of interesting pharmacological effects on the human body, such as drowsiness, weight loss, antinociceptive, and antioxidant properties, among other advantages.

Crinum Asiaticum

There are about 80 genera and 2200 recognised species in the Amaryllidaceae family, which is divided into three subfamilies: Agapanthideae, Alliioideae, and Amaryllidoideae². The Amaryllidoideae family is a significant source of alkaloids, and its members have acetylcholinesterase [AChE] inhibitory, antioxidant, antidiabetic, anticancer, antiviral, antiparasitic, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective properties. The majority of research on amaryllidaceae alkaloids used to treat Alzheimer's disease (AD) has concentrated on testing them for AChE inhibitory activity using various structural kinds³.

PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS :

Phytochemicals have been linked to health advantages for millennia, and this association is still present in modern medications. Only a small percentage of the 350,699 recognised plant species listed by The Plant List have had their phytochemical profiles examined⁴. Drug research depends on the identification of bioactive chemicals from plants, hence screening plants for these molecules is quite interesting. This section provides a summary of the chemical characterisation of *C. asiaticum* that has

been done thus far, taking into account the chemicals found in various extracts and the plant's essential oils.

A significant member of the Amaryllidaceae family, the *Crinum* genus contains elements from several phytochemical classes, including coumarins, alkaloids, terpenoids, and flavanoids. These chemical classes' compounds are in charge of crucial biological functions like antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities⁵.

The Phytochemicals constituents of *Crinum Asiaticum* consists are of following;

1. ALKALOIDS
2. PHENOLS
3. ALDEHYDES
4. TERPENOIDS
5. ALCOHOL
6. FATTY ACIDS
7. ESTERS
8. SESQUITERPENES

PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES :

The pharmacological characteristics of the *Crinum Asiaticum* plant include:

- * Analgesic & Anti-Inflammatory

- * Antioxidant Property
- * Other pharmacological properties
- * Antimicrobial properties
- * Cytotoxicity and anticancer properties

1. Antioxidant property:

The antioxidant activity of *C. asiaticum* has been emphasised in numerous investigations. As one example, has documented that lycorine (9) and the ethanolic extract of *C. asiaticum* demonstrated protective benefits on human erythrocytes, which were attributed to their antioxidant qualities against oxidative damage caused by 2-amidinopropane⁶.

According to the results, lycorine (9) and the ethanolic extract of *C. asiaticum* leaf both shown strong free radical scavenging activity against 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radicals in a dose-dependent manner, with the *C. asiaticum* extract being more effective than the lycorine.

2. Analgesia and Anti-inflammatory Property :

Many authors have looked at *C. asiaticum* anti-inflammatory qualities. Of these, investigated the effect of Malaysian on inflammation. In the experimental model, *C. asiaticum* leaf extracts in chloroform and methanol (50 mg/kg, orally) demonstrated potent anti-inflammatory properties that were superior to those of indomethacin⁷. Intriguingly, a group of individuals patented topical and cosmetic formulations in 2005 that included *C. asiaticum* extract as an active ingredient to decrease at an effective dose.

3. Cytotoxicity and anti-cancer property:

A general bioassay, the brine shrimp lethality assay can identify a wide range of bioactivities, such as

cytotoxicity and antibacterial properties. Remarkably, found that the methanolic extract of *C. asiaticum* leaves had the strongest cytotoxic activity on murine P388 D1 cells. However, the study conducted by ⁸ showed that *C. asiaticum* hot water extracts significantly reduced the cytotoxicity caused by calprotectin in MM46 mouse mammary cancer cells.

4. Antimicrobial properties:

According to research, *C. asiaticum* exhibits a wide range of antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria as well as fungal diseases. With MIC values of 1.25, 0.078, and 0.078 mg/ml, respectively, the study by shown that the essential oil of *C. asiaticum* leaves had strong antibacterial action against *Shigella boydii*, *Candida albicans*, and *Rhizopus* sp. Furthermore, it has been shown that the essential oil and extracts of *C. asiaticum* have antifungal properties against five pathogenic fungus⁹.

5. Other pharmacological properties :

C. asiaticum var. *japonicum* Baker extract has been shown to have an anti-obesity effect. The ethanolic extract of the plant's aerial parts has demonstrated activity against adipocyte differentiation and lipogenesis by suppressing the expression of adipocyte protein, C/EBPCCAAT/enhancer-binding protein b, and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor g. Another study by showed that norgalanthamine and extract from *C. asiaticum* var. *japonicum* may affect hair development by inhibiting the TGF- β 1-induced canonical pathway and 5 α -reductase activity. There have also been reports of *C. asiaticum*'s ability to heal wound. In light exhibited prohealing benefits when applied topically¹⁰.

LIST OF REASEARCH ARTICLES ON CRINUM ASIATICUM

S. N O	Title of research	Author	Summary	Refere nce
1.	Palmilycorine and lycorisode :acyloxy and acylglucosyloxy alkaloids from crinum asiaticum	ShibnathGhos al, Amrithalinga mShanthy, Anandkumar, Yatendrakum ar ,1985”	The fruits of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> yielded two novel alkaloidal conjugates: an acylglucosyloxy derivative called lycorisode and a C16-acyloxy derivative called palmilycorine. The fleshy scale leaves and roots of this species were also found to contain similar chemicals. Based on thorough spectrum evidence and chemical transformation, the two compounds' structures were determined to be 1-O-palmitoyllycorine (1) and lycorine-1-O-(6'- O-palmitoyl- β -D-glucopyranoside) (2), respectively	11

2.	Crinum alkaloids :their chemistry and biology	ShibnathGhos al ,Kulwant S. Saini, SushmaRazda , 1985	This review covers the present state of research on free and glycosylated alkaloids found in species of the genus Crinum. These alkaloids' spectrum characteristics, structural characteristics, distribution, isolation, interconventions, and biological activities are discussed.	12
3.	Isocraugsodine, an n-arylidenephenethyl amine from Crinum asiaticum and its e- z isomerism	ShibnathGhosa l, Amirthalingam Shanthi, Sushil K. Singh ,1988	Isocraugsodine, a novel Schiff's base, was extracted from Crinum asiaticum fruits. On the basis of thorough spectroscopic evidence and chemical transformation, its N-(3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzylidene)- 4'-hydroxyphenethylamine structure was determined. Using high resolution 1H NMR analysis, the temperature-gradient distribution of the three isomeric forms (1a⇌1b⇌1c) of the Schiff's base was identified	13
4.	Effects of stress on alkaloid metabolism in Crinum asiaticum	ShibnathGhos al, Sushil K. Singh, Sankara G. Unnikrishnan ,1990	The biochemical function of both free and conjugated alkaloids in Crinum asiaticum fruits during strees— incisional damage and insect attack—is evaluated. In addition to producing oxidized metabolises of lycorine and its analogues, wounding C. asiaticum fruits resulted in nearly total hydrolysis of the alkaloidal conjugates. Fruits that had previously been treated with anesthetics, such as ether and lidocaine, were shielded against hydrolysis and oxidation by the alkaloidal conjugates.	14
5.	Crinum species in traditional and modern medicine	C.W Fennel, J van Staden , 2001	Crinums are big, ostentatious plants with umbels of flowers that resemble lilies. They are prevalent in tropical and subtropical areas of the world, and they have been used historically to treat illnesses and maladies for ages. They are occasionally administered for the same medical condition.	15
6.	Crinum L. (Amaryllidaceae)	Nguyen Thi Ngoc Tram a , Tz.VTitorenk ova b , V St. Bankova b, N.V,Handjiev a b S.S Popov ,2002	The alkaloids that were isolated from Crinum species between 1985 and 2000 have been reviewed. This is the first survey of non- nitrogenous chemicals. Topics covered include biological activity and botanical taxonomy. The sources of the literature on spectral data are provided.	16

7.	Molecular cloning and characterization of a mannose-binding lectin gene from <i>Crinum asiaticum</i>	Yourong Chai a b d , Yongzhen Pang c , Zhihua Liao,2003	<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> var. <i>sinicum</i> is a traditional Chinese medicinal herb whose full-length cDNA of an agglutinin or mannose-binding lectin gene was cloned using RACE-PCR. <i>C. asiaticum</i> agglutinin (caa) had a 528 bp open reading frame in its 820 bp full-length cDNA that encoded a 22 aa signal peptide and a lectin precursor (preproprotein) with 175 amino acid residues.	17
8.	A new phenolic compound from <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.	Qian Sun a , Wei Dong Zhang a b, Yun Heng Shen a , Chuan Zhang a ,2008	The ethanol extract of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L. var. <i>sinicum</i> Baker bulbs yielded a novel phenolic component. Based on spectroscopic data, its structure was determined to be 1-(2-hydroxy-4- hydroxymethyl)phenyl-6-O-caffeoyl- β -D-glucopyranoside.	18
9	Crinummin, a chymotrypsin-like but glycosylated serine protease from <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> : Purification and physicochemical characterisation	KunwarAwaneesh Singh a , Reetesh Kumar b , G.R.K. Rao a , Medicherla V. Jagannadham b , 2010	Cation-exchange column chromatography was used to separate Crinummin, a glycosylated serine protease with chymotrypsin-like activity, from the latex of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> . In addition to being effective against chaotrophs, organic solvents, and detergents, crinummin exhibits activity throughout a broad pH range (4.5–11.5 with an optimum at 8.5) and temperature range (75 °C with an optimum at 70 °C), even after extended exposure.	19
10	Thrombolytic along with anti-platelet activity of crinummin, a protein constituent of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i>	KunwarAwaneesh Singh a , Manasa K. Nayak a , Medicherla V. Jagannadham b , Debabrata Dash a ,2011	Thrombotic illnesses are treated with a variety of anticoagulants, anti-platelet, and thrombolytic medicines. Anti-coagulants and anti-platelet medicines do not break up blood clots; they only stop them from forming in the first place. As demonstrated by photography serine protease that exhibits plasmin-like fibrinolytic activity and suppresses platelet aggregation and P-selectin exposure.	20
11	Ethanol extract of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> attenuates hyperglycemia-mediated oxidative stress and protects hepatocytes in alloxan induced experimental diabetic rats	S. Indradevi a , S. Ilavenil a, B. Kaleeswaran a, S. Srigopalram b ,2012	The current study aims to examine the antioxidant activity in diabetic rats that have been given alloxan. Three groups were randomly selected from among the experimental rats: Group I was the control group; Group II was the alloxan-induced diabetic group; and Group III was the alloxan-induced diabetic group that received treatment with an ethanolic extract of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> leaves (200 mg/kg/bw).	21

12.	Antioxidant, anti-diabetic, acetylcholinesterase inhibitory potential and estimation of alkaloids (lycorine and galanthamine) from <i>Crinum</i> species: An important source of anticancer and anti-Alzheimer drug	S.G. Ghane a , U.A. Attar a , P.B. Yadav b , M.M. Lekhak ,2018	The bulbous monocot <i>Crinum</i> L. (Amaryllidaceae J. St. Hil.) is renowned for both its therapeutic and decorative qualities. Twelve genotypes of <i>Crinum</i> were examined for their phytochemicals, antioxidants, in vitro anti-diabetic, and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitory properties in aqueous and methanolic leaf extracts. This study is the first to compare antioxidants, phenolic profile, anti-diabetic potential, and the simultaneous measurement of anti-cancer and anti-Alzheimer medications, namely LY and GAL, from <i>Crinum</i> genotypes.	22
13.	Efficient polysaccharides from <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.'s structural characterization and anti-tumor effect	Miao Yu a c , Yingxiang Chen a , Yingjie Liu ,2019	An effective polysaccharide with a molecular weight of 730,000 Da, called CAL-n (<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.-n), was isolated and refined from <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L for the first time in this study. With a molar ratio of 1:61.6:1.66:4.74, CAL-n was made up of Rha (rhamnose), Sor (sorboside), Gal (galactose), and Glu (glucose). CAL-n's chemical structure was investigated using GC-MS (Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometer) analysis and infrared spectrum analysis.	23
14.	Response surface method was used to optimize the	Miao Yu a c , Bing Wang b , Zheng Qi a ,2019	This work used response surface methodology (RSM) to investigate ultrasound-assisted flavonoid extraction from <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> in order to	
	ultrasonic assisted extraction of flavonoids from <i>Crinum asiaticum</i>		determine the optimal flavonoid extraction procedure and increase the flavonoid extraction rate. In the subsequent RSM experiment, we used the center point of each factor's corresponding data from the single-factor tests, and we then performed multiple regression analysis on the experimental data.	24
15.	Alkaloids with anti-human carbonic anhydrase isozyme II activity from the bulbs of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L. var. <i>asiaticum</i>	WaraluckChai chompoo a , Ratchanaporn Chokchaisiri b , Anyaporn Sangkaew c , Wachirachai Pabuprapap a , Chulee Yompa kdee c ,2020	The bulbs of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L. var. <i>asiaticum</i> were used to isolate fifteen recognized alkaloids 3–17 as well as two new haemanthamine-type alkaloids, crinasiaticine A (1) and crinasiaticine B (2). Spectroscopic analysis was used to determine the structures of the new compounds, and spectral comparison with previously published compounds was used to identify the known compounds.	25

16.	Comparative antioxidant and antimicrobial potentials of leaf successive extract fractions of poison bulb, <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.	Souren Goswami, Ria Das, Poulomi Ghosh, Tista Chakraborty, Anuva Barman, Sanjib Ray, 2020	The Amaryllidaceae family includes the extensively used medicinal plant species <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L., which has significant ethnomedicinal uses. Using the phenolic content of <i>C. asiaticum</i> leaf extracts, the current work sought to assess their in vitro antioxidant and antibacterial effects. Their antioxidant potential was assessed using the ferric ion reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay, 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging activity, and total antioxidant assay of the leaf crude aqueous extract and the five successive extract fractions.	26
17.	Ethnomedicinal, phytochemistry, toxicity and pharmacological benefits of poison bulb – <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.	M.F. Mahomoodally, N.B. Sadeer, S. Suroowan, S. Jugreet, D. Lobine, 2021	The perennial bulbous herb <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L. (Amaryllidaceae), sometimes referred to as spider lily or poison bulb, has fluffy green leaves and is used to cause vomiting when poisoning. It is referred to as "naagadami" in Ayurveda, "bakong" by the locals in Malaysia, "morabau" in Papua New Guinea, and "lys" or "lissauvage" in Mauritius. Chemical examination of essential oils extracted from <i>C. asiaticum</i> showed the presence of several components such as alcohols, phenolics, fatty acids, esters, aldehydes, terpenoids, and terpenes. It was discovered that <i>C. asiaticum</i> was especially rich in alkaloids.	27
18.	Acute and sub-acute toxicity studies of the chloroform extract of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> bulbs in mice.	Michael Ofori, Cynthia Amaning Danquah, Paul Poku Sampene Ossei, Gilbert Rahaman, Williams Adu Asamoah, 2021	This study's objective is to evaluate the chloroform extract of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> bulbs' (CCA) acute and subacute toxicity profile in ICR mice. Healthy male and non-pregnant female ICR mice weighing 15–20 g were used in the acute toxicity test. The majority of the evidence points to the Asian origin of <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> . The bulbs of this plant are extensively dispersed throughout areas of Africa and Asia.	28
19.	Catalytic activity of silver nanoparticles synthesized using <i>Crinum asiaticum</i>	Samiksha Shukla, Anne Masih, Aryan, Mohan Singh	Recent years have seen a rise in the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs), which is a simple, non-toxic, economical, and environmentally friendly use of precursors. Using green leaves from <i>Crinum asiaticum</i> , the study	
	(Sudarshan) leaf extract	Mehata, 2022	offers a sustainable method of creating Ag-NPs and investigates how the biomolecules found in the plant contribute to the production of Ag-NPs.	29

20.	Betulin and Crinum asiaticum L. bulbs extract attenuate pulmonary fibrosis by down regulating pro-fibrotic and pro-inflammatory cytokines in bleomycin- induced fibrosis mice model	Michael Ofori a b , Cynthia AmaningDan quah b , Joshua Asante b, SelaseAtivu i b , Peace Doe c , Alhassan Abdul-NasirTaribabu b,2023	The lung condition known as pulmonary fibrosis (PF) is characterized by lung tissue scarring that affects lung function. People with pulmonary fibrosis are expected to live for three to five years. In therapeutic settings, bleomycin (BLM) is used to treat testicular germ-cell malignancies and Hodgkin lymphoma. The way bleomycin works is by preventing the creation of proteins and DNA.	30
21	Isolation of bioactive phytochemicals from Crinum asiaticum L. along with their cytotoxic and TRAIL-resistance abrogating prospect assessment	Sharmin Ahmed Rakhi a , Yasumasa Hara b , Md. Saiful Islam a c , TeruhisaManome b , SafaetAlam d aNazimUddin Emon ,2024	The perennial bulbous herb Crinum asiaticum L. (Amaryllidaceae) is used locally for its many pharmacological qualities, which include anticancer, immune-stimulating, analgesic, antiviral, antimalarial, antibacterial, and antifungal effects, as well as its aesthetic appeal. Three recognized compounds were obtained from the separation of C. asiaticum leaf MeOH extract: cycloneolitsol (1), hippeastrine (2), and β - sitosterol.	31
22.	Acetylcholinesterase inhibition studies of alkaloid components from Crinum asiaticum var. sinicum: in vitro assessments by molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations	Ngo Viet Duc, Vu ThiTrang , Hoang Le Tuan Anh , Le Ba Vinh , Nguyen Viet Phong , Tran QuangThuan , Ngo Van Hieu, Nguyen TienDat , Le Van Nhan ,2024	The perennial bulbous herb Crinum asiaticum L. (Amaryllidaceae) is used locally for its many pharmacological qualities, which include anticancer, immune-stimulating, analgesic, antiviral, antimalarial, antibacterial, and antifungal effects, as well as its aesthetic appeal. Three recognized compounds were obtained from the separation of C. asiaticum leaf MeOH extract: cycloneolitsol (1), hippeastrine (2), and β - sitosterol (3).	32

REFERENCES:

1. Tram, N.T.N., Titorenkova, T.V., Bankova, V.S., Handjieva, N., Popov, S. Crinum (Amaryllidaceae). *Fitoterapia* . 2002 ;73 (3), 183-208.
2. Caruso, G., Golubkina, N., Tallarita, A., Abdelhamid, M.T., Sekara, A., 2020.
3. Cortes, N., Posada, R.A., Alvarez, R., Alzate, F., Berkov, S., Cardona, G.P., Osorio, E., Neuroprotective activity and acetylcholinesterase inhibition of five Amaryllidaceae species: a comparative study. *Life Sci.* 2015 ; 122, 42–50.
4. Brielmann, H.L., Setzer, W.N., Kaufman, P.B., Kirakosyan, A, Cseke, L.J... Phyto-chemicals: the chemical components plants. *Natural Products from Plants* 2006 ;1-49.
5. Celikel. N. Kavas, G. Antimicrobial properties of some essential oils against some pathogenic microorganisms. *Czech Journal of Food Sciences-UZPI (Czech Republic)* 2008; 26, 174-181.
6. Ilaivelil, S., Kaleeswaran, B., Sumitha, P., Tamilvendan, D., Ravikumar, S. Protection of human erythrocyte using Crinum asiaticum extract and lycorine from oxidative damage induced by 2-amidinopropane. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences* 2011; 18(2), 181–187.
7. Samud, A.M., Asmawi, M.Z., Sharma, J.N., Yusof, A.P.M. Anti-inflammatory activity of Crinum asiaticum plant and its effect on bradykinin-induced contractions on isolated uterus. *Immunopharmacology* 1999 ; 43 (2), 311–316.
8. Yui, S., Mikami, M., Kitahara, M., Yamazaki, M. The inhibitory effect of lycorine on tumor cell apoptosis induced by polymorphonuclear leukocyte-derived calprotecin. *Immunopharmacology* 1998; 40 (2), 151–162.
9. Fu. Jh., Cao, Luo, Y.p. The antifungal activities and GC-MS analysis of the essential oil from Crinum asiaticum. *Guangdong Agricultural Sciences* 2012 ; 19.
10. Kang, J.-I., Choi, J.H., Lee, J.G., Yoo, E.-S., Kim, Y.H., Kang, H.-K. The Mechanism of Crinum asiaticum var. japonicum on the Activation of Anagen. *Korean Journal of Pharmacognosy* 2017; 48 (2), 148–154.
11. Shibnath Ghosal, Amirthalingam Shanthi, Anand Kumar, Yatendra Kumar Palmilycorine and lycorinide: acyloxy and acylglucosyloxy alkaloids from crinum asiaticum *Phytochemistry* 29 October 1985 ; Volume 24(11) , Pages 2703-2706.
12. Shibnath Ghosal Kulwant S. Saini Sushma Razdan Crinum alkaloids: their chemistry and biology *Phytochemistry* 1985; Volume 24 (10), Pages 2141-2156 .
13. Shibnath Ghosal Amirthalingam Shanthi Sushil K. Singh Isocraugsodine, an n-arylidenephenethylamine from Crinum asiaticum and its e-z isomerism *Phytochemistry* 1988; Volume 27(6), Pages 1849-1852.
14. Shibnath Ghosal Sushil K. Singh Sankara G. Unnikrishnan Effects of stress on alkaloid metabolism in Crinum asiaticum *Phytochemistry* 1990; Volume 29(3), Pages 805-811C.
15. W Fennell J van Staden Crinum species in traditional and modern medicine *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* November 2001 ;Volume 78(1), Pages 15-26.
16. Nguyen Thi Ngoc Tram a , Tz.V Titorenkova b V St. Bankova b ,N.V Handjieva b , S.S Popov b Crinum L. (Amaryllidaceae) *Fitoterapia* June 2002; Volume 73(3), Pages 183-208.
17. Yourong Chai a b d Yongzhen Pang c Zhihua Liao c L.e.i. Zhang a c Xiaofen Sun c Yongquan Lu a Sangen Wang b Kexuan Tang a c Molecular cloning and characterization of a mannose-binding lectin gene from Crinum asiaticum *Journal of Plant Physiology* 2003;Volume 160 (8), Pages 913-920.
18. Qian Sun a Wei Dong Zhang a b ,Yun Heng Shen a Chuan Zhang a ,Hui Liang Li a A new phenolic compound from Crinum asiaticum L. *Chinese Chemical Letters* April 2008, Pages 447-449.
19. Kunwar Awaneesh Singh a Reetesh Kumar b G.R.K. Rao a Medicherla V. Jagannadham b Crinum, a chymotrypsin-like but glycosylated serine protease from Crinum asiaticum: Purification and physicochemical characterisation *Food Chemistry* 15 April 2010 ;Volume 119(4), Pages 1352-1358.
20. Kunwar Awaneesh Singh a Manasa K. Nayak a Medicherla V. Jagannadham b Debabrata Dash a Thrombolytic along with anti-platelet activity of crinum, a protein constituent of Crinum asiaticum *Blood Cells, Molecules, and Diseases* 15 August 2011; Volume 47(2) ,Pages 129-132.
21. S. Indradevi a S. Ilavenil a, B. Kaleeswaran a S. Srigopalram S. Ravikumar a Ethanolic extract of Crinum asiaticum attenuates hyperglycemia-mediated oxidative stress and protects hepatocytes in alloxan induced experimental diabetic rats *Journal of King Saud University – Science* April 2012 ;Volume 24(2) , Pages 171-177.
22. S.G. Ghane a U.A. Attar a P.B. Yadav b M.M. Lekhak b Antioxidant, anti-diabetic, acetylcholinesterase inhibitory potential and estimation of alkaloids (lycorine and

- galanthamine) from *Crinum* species: An important source of anticancer and anti-Alzheimer drug. *Industrial Crops and Products* 1 December 2018; Volume 125, Pages 168-177.
23. Miao Yu a c Yingxiang Chen a Yingjie Liu a c Miao Yu a Ying Xu a Bing Wang b Efficient polysaccharides from *Crinum asiaticum* L.'s structural characterization and anti-tumor effect *Saudi Journal of Biological Science* December 2019 ;Volume 26 (8), Pages 2085-2090.
 24. Miao Yu a c Bing Wang b Zheng Qi a Guosong Xin a c Wenlan Li a c Response surface method was used to optimize the ultrasonic assisted extraction of flavonoids from *Crinum asiaticum* *Saudi Journal of Biological Science*, December 2019 ;Volume 26 (8), Pages 2079- 2084.
 25. Waraluck Chaichompoo a Ratchanaporn Chokchaisiri b Anyaporn Sangkaew c Wachirachai Pabuprapap a Chulee Yompakdee c Apichart Suksamrarn a Alkaloids with anti-human carbonic anhydrase isozyme II activity from the bulbs of *Crinum asiaticum* L. var. *asiaticum* *Phytochemistry Letters*, June 2020 ; Volume 37, Pages 101-105.
 26. Souren Goswami Ria Das Poulomi Ghosh Tista Chakraborty Anuva Barman Sanjib Ray Comparative antioxidant and antimicrobial potentials of leaf successive extract fractions of poison bulb, *Crinum asiaticum* L. *Industrial Crops and Product* 15 October 2020 ;Volume 154,e 112667.
 27. M.F. Mahomoodally a b N.B. Sadeer c S. Suroowan c S. Jugreet c D. Lobine c K.R.R. Rengasamy d Ethnomedicinal, phytochemistry, toxicity and pharmacological benefits of poison bulb – *Crinum asiaticum* L. *South African Journal of Botany* January 2021 ;Volume 136, Pages 16-29.
 28. Michael Ofori a Cynthia Amaning Danquah a Paul Poku Sampene Ossei b Gilbrene Rahamani a c Williams Adu Asamoah a Selasie Ativui a Peace Doe Acute and sub-acute toxicity studies of the chloroform extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs in mice *South African Journal of Botany* December 2021 ;Volume 143, Pages 133-140.
 29. Samiksha Shukla 1 Anne Masih 1 Aryan Mohan Singh Mehata Catalytic activity of silver nanoparticles synthesized using *Crinum asiaticum* (Sudarshan) leaf extract *Materials Today: Proceeding* 2022 ; Volume 56, Part 6, Pages 3714-3720.
 30. Michael Ofori, b Michof2825@gmail.com · Cynthia Amaning Danquah b · Joshua Asanteb, d · Selase Ativuib · Peace Doec · Alhassan Abdul-Nasir Taribabub · Isaac Newton Nugbemadob · Adwoa Nkrumah Mensahb Betulin and *Crinum asiaticum* L. bulbs extract attenuate pulmonary fibrosis by down regulating pro-fibrotic and pro-inflammatory cytokines in bleomycin-induced fibrosis mice model RESEARCH ARTICLE June 2023 ;Volume 9 (6) ,e16914 .
 31. Harmin Ahmed Rakhia · Yasumasa Harab · Md. Saiful Islama, c · Teruhisa Manomeb · Safaet Alamd, a · Nazim Uddin Emone · Muhammad Abdullah Al-Mansurf · Md. Ruhul Kuddusa · Md. Raihan Sarkarg · Masami Ishibashib · Firoj Ahmedh firoj72@du.ac.bd Isolation of bioactive phytochemicals from *Crinum asiaticum* L. along with their cytotoxic and TRAIL- resistance abrogating prospect assessment Research article February 15, 2024 ; Volume 10 (3), e25049 .
 32. Ngo Viet Duc, Vu Thi Trang, Hoang Le Tuan Anh, Le Ba Vinh, Nguyen Viet Phong, Tran Quang Thuan, Ngo Van Hieu, Nguyen Tien Dat, Le Van Nhan, Do Thanh Tuan, Le Tuan Anh, Do Thi Thao, Bui Huu Tai, Nguyen Cao Cuong, Le Quynh Lien & Seo Young Yang Acetylcholinesterase inhibition studies of alkaloid components from *Crinum asiaticum* var. *sinicum*: in vitro assessments by molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations *Journal of Asian Natural Products Research* 2024; Volume 26 (5).